

A Study on Fiber Reinforced Concrete Containing Alccofine and Dolomite Powder as Supplementary Cementitious Material

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ABSTRACT

Steel fibers are incorporated into the mixture to enhance the structural qualities of steel fiber-reinforced concrete (SFRC), a specific type of fiber-reinforced concrete. Steel fibers greatly increase the concrete's strength, and resistance to cracking and deformation, making it appropriate for a range of applications requiring load-bearing capacity and strength. Mechanical performance can be enhanced with Alccofine, a superfine mineral addition derived from slag-based minerals. The natural mineral dolomite powder, which is made up of calcium magnesium carbonate ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$), has qualities that lower costs, increase sustainability, and improve the performance of concrete. Dolomite powder and Alccofine work effectively together to increase the strength of concrete while lowering its environmental impact, making this combination an affordable and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional building methods. Alccofine (Partial Replacement of cement) lowers the carbon footprint of concrete manufacturing while improving long-term strength, durability, and resistance to chemical attacks. As a filler material, dolomite powder (Partial Replacement of cement) improves the concrete's microstructure, reduces voids, and increases compactness. The combined impacts of these materials on compressive, flexural, and tensile strength will be assessed in this study. This study aims to investigate if adding steel fibers improves tensile and flexural strength significantly, Non-Destructive Tests (Rebound hammer and USPVP) will be carried out to support the results obtained by tests mentioned above.

Keywords: Steel fibers, Alccofine, Dolomite powder, Rebound hammer, Ultrasonic pulse velocity (USPV), Compressive Test, Split tensile Test, Flexural strength Test.

1. INTRODUCTION: Concrete is the most widely used construction material in civil engineering due to its strength, durability, and versatility. However, the growing demand for concrete has led to increased cement consumption, raising serious environmental concerns because cement production is energy-intensive and a major source of carbon dioxide emissions. Consequently, reducing cement content through partial replacement with alternative materials has become an important focus in sustainable construction. Supplementary cementitious materials are commonly used to enhance concrete performance while minimizing environmental impact. Alccofine is an ultrafine mineral admixture derived from slag-based materials, known for its high reactivity and fineness. When used as a partial replacement for cement, it enhances hydration, improves particle packing, and increases strength and durability by reducing permeability and improving resistance to aggressive environments. Dolomite powder, a naturally occurring calcium magnesium carbonate, primarily acts as a micro-filler within the cementitious matrix. Its fine particles reduce voids, improve compactness, and enhance microstructure, while also offering economic benefits due to its availability and lower cost.

The combined use of Alccofine and dolomite powder provides an effective means of reducing cement content while maintaining desirable strength characteristics. While Alccofine contributes to strength through its reactive nature, dolomite powder improves physical packing and matrix density.

However, reduced cement content may adversely affect tensile and flexural strength. To address this limitation, steel fibers are incorporated as discrete reinforcement to control crack propagation, enhance ductility, and improve post-cracking behaviour. The present study evaluates the feasibility of producing sustainable and structurally efficient concrete by partially replacing cement with Alccofine and dolomite powder and incorporating steel fibers. Mechanical properties such as compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength are assessed, along with non-destructive tests including rebound hammer and ultrasonic pulse velocity to evaluate concrete quality and uniformity.

1.1 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study investigates the effect of partial replacement of cement with Alccofine and dolomite powder, along with the addition of steel fibers, on the performance of concrete. Alccofine and dolomite powder are used as supplementary cementitious materials to reduce cement content and improve the microstructural and mechanical properties of concrete. Alccofine, Dolomite is incorporated at various proportions. Where, Alccofine as replacement levels of cement, and dolomite powder is used in varying proportions as a filler material. Steel fibers are added in controlled percentages as an additive to improve tensile and flexural behaviour. Concrete specimens are cast and tested at 7, 28, and 56 days to evaluate compressive strength. Split tensile strength and flexural strength tests are conducted at appropriate curing ages to assess the influence of cement replacement and fiber addition on tensile performance. Fresh concrete properties such as workability are evaluated through slump tests. Non-destructive tests including rebound hammer and ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) are performed to assess surface hardness, internal quality, and to establish correlation with destructive test results. The objectives of this study are to:

- Assess the mechanical performance of concrete incorporating Alccofine and dolomite powder as partial replacements for cement.
- Evaluate the effect of steel fibers as an additive on tensile and flexural strength of concrete with reduced cement content.
- Study the workability characteristics of concrete mixes containing Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fibers.
- Examine the feasibility of using Alccofine and dolomite powder for producing sustainable and economical concrete.
- Correlate results obtained from non-destructive tests with destructive strength parameters.
- Identify optimum replacement and additive proportions that provide improved strength and durability performance.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akula Rajani and Kurendha Geetha (2020) investigated the influence of Alccofine and the combined effect of Alccofine with steel fibers on the mechanical properties of concrete. Cement was partially replaced with Alccofine at levels of 5%, 10%, and 15%, while crimped circular steel fibers were added at 1% by volume of concrete. The study reported that compressive, flexural, and splitting tensile strengths increased with an increase in Alccofine content, with the optimum performance observed for concrete containing 15% Alccofine in combination with steel fibers. The improvement in mechanical properties was attributed to enhanced particle packing, refinement of the pore structure, densification of the cementitious matrix, and the effective crack-bridging action of steel fibers, leading to superior performance compared to conventional concrete.

Srinath B.L.N., C.K Patnaikuni (2022). Reviewed the performance of Alccofine as a supplementary cementitious material in concrete. Their study highlighted that due to its ultrafine particle size and high reactivity, Alccofine improves particle packing, accelerates hydration, and enhances early and long-term strength of concrete. The authors concluded that partial replacement of cement with

Alccofine in the range of 5–15% significantly improves compressive strength and durability characteristics.

Oviya and Anusiya (2017) conducted an experimental and analytical study on the mechanical properties of steel fiber reinforced concrete for M40 and M50 grades using hooked-end and crimped steel fibers at volume fractions of 0.5% and 1%. The study reported that the inclusion of steel fibers marginally improved compressive strength while significantly enhancing flexural strength, modulus of elasticity, and overall ductility of concrete. For the same volume fraction, hooked-end steel fibers consistently exhibited better performance compared to crimped fibers due to improved mechanical bonding and crack-arresting capability. The authors also demonstrated that artificial neural network (ANN) models could accurately predict strength parameters, showing close agreement with experimental results

Srinivasan (2020) investigated the performance of Alccofine-1203 as a partial replacement of cement in high-performance concrete (HPC), focusing on mechanical and durability characteristics of M50 grade concrete. Cement was replaced with Alccofine at 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%, and the concrete was evaluated for compressive strength, flexural strength, modulus of elasticity, and durability properties. The study reported that concrete containing 10% Alccofine exhibited optimum performance, showing notable improvement in compressive and flexural strengths as well as elastic modulus compared to the control mix. Beyond this replacement level, Alccofine primarily acted as a filler, resulting in reduced strength but improved workability. The enhanced performance at optimum dosage was attributed to improved particle packing, reduced porosity, and a denser cementitious matrix, confirming the suitability of Alccofine for producing

Gund K.C., and Patwari V.G. (2020) conducted an experimental study on the partial replacement of cement with dolomite powder in concrete to evaluate its effect on mechanical properties. Cement was replaced with dolomite powder at levels of 5%, 10%, and 15% by weight, and the concrete was tested for compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength. The study reported that dolomite powder primarily acts as a filler material, improving particle packing and compactness of the concrete matrix. An increase in strength was observed up to an optimum replacement level of 10%, beyond which the strength decreased due to the inert nature of dolomite powder and reduced availability of reactive cementitious material. The authors concluded that dolomite powder can be effectively used as a cost-effective and sustainable cement replacement at limited dosages

3. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3.1 MATERIALS USED

A. Cement:

Ordinary Portland Cement of 53 grade (OPC 53) was used in the present study. The cement had a specific gravity of 3.15.

B. Fine Aggregate:

Fine aggregate used in this investigation consisted of clean, well-graded natural sand passing through a 4.75 mm sieve. The physical properties of the sand were determined through laboratory testing. The sand exhibited a specific gravity of 2.74 and the fine aggregate was classified as Zone II, making it suitable for use in concrete as per relevant Indian Standards.

C. Coarse Aggregate:

The coarse aggregate used in this study comprised locally sourced crushed stone aggregates with a nominal maximum size of 20 mm. The aggregates were tested as per IS 2386 (Part III):1963 to determine their physical and mechanical properties. The specific gravity of the coarse aggregate was found to be 2.68.

D. Alccofine:

Alccofine was used in this study as a partial replacement for cement. It is an ultrafine mineral admixture obtained from slag-based materials. The Alccofine used had a light grey colour and very fine

particle size, which helps in improving particle packing and hydration. The specific gravity of Alccofine was about 2.90. Due to its high fineness, it increases the surface area available for reaction and contributes to better strength development.

E. Dolomite Powder:

It is used as a partial replacement for cement in the concrete mixes. It is a naturally occurring mineral obtained by grinding dolomite rock. The powder used in this study was fine, uniform, and light in color. The specific gravity of dolomite powder was found to be approximately 2.85. Due to its fine nature, dolomite powder mainly acts as a filler material and helps in improving the compactness of the concrete matrix.

F. Steel Fibers:

Steel fibers were added to the concrete as an additive to improve tensile and flexural performance. The fibers used were short, discrete steel fibers with uniform geometry. The specific gravity of steel fibers was about 7.85. The fibers possessed high tensile strength and stiffness, which makes them effective in controlling crack formation and propagation.

G. Superplasticizer (Conplast SP 430):

Conplast SP 430 was used in the present study as a high-range water-reducing admixture to improve the workability of concrete without increasing the water content. It is a sulphonated naphthalene formaldehyde (SNF)-based superplasticizer supplied in liquid form. The admixture was dark brown in colour and completely soluble in water. The specific gravity of Conplast SP 430 was approximately 1.18.

H. Water:

Concrete must be mixed with clean water that has no dangerous quantities oils, organic compounds, acids, and alkalis or other deleterious chemicals. In this investigation, we used portable tap water from the JNTUA college campus water plant that met the IS456-2000 standards for casting concrete and curing the specimens.

3.2 MIX PROPORTION:

To achieve M40 grade concrete, the mix design was carried out in accordance with IS 10262:2009. In the present study, cement was partially replaced with Alccofine at replacement levels of 5%, 10%, and 15% by weight of cement. In addition, dolomite powder was used as a supplementary material at replacement levels of 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% by weight of cement. Steel fibers were added to all concrete mixes at a constant dosage of 0.5% by volume of concrete to improve tensile and flexural performance.

3.3 CASTING OF SPECIMENS:

For each mix proportion, concrete specimens were prepared and tested to evaluate the mechanical properties. Cube specimens were cast to determine compressive strength, while cylinders and beams were cast for split tensile and flexural strength tests, respectively. The specimens were cured and tested at 7, 28, and 56 days. The primary objective of this mix proportioning was to identify the optimum combination of Alccofine and dolomite powder that provides improved strength, while steel fibers were used as an additive to enhance crack resistance and overall structural performance.

3.4 Testing Methods

3.4.1 Workability Test:

Workability of fresh concrete is an important property that indicates the ease with which concrete can be mixed, placed, compacted, and finished without segregation or excessive bleeding. In the present study, the workability of concrete mixes was evaluated using the slump test. This test is commonly adopted

due to its simplicity and effectiveness in assessing the consistency of fresh concrete. The slump test was carried out using a standard slump cone placed on a non-absorbent surface. Freshly mixed concrete was poured into the cone in layers and each layer was compacted properly. After filling, the cone was slowly lifted in a vertical direction, allowing the concrete to settle under its own weight. The reduction in height of the concrete, known as slump, was measured immediately. The measured slump value was used to assess the workability of the concrete mixes containing Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fibers.

3.4.2 Compressive Strength Test:

The compressive strength of concrete was evaluated by casting cube specimens of size 150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm. M40 grade concrete was prepared using Ordinary Portland Cement, fine aggregate, 20 mm nominal size coarse aggregate, with partial replacement of cement by Alccofine at 5%, 10%, and 15% and dolomite powder at 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%, while steel fibers were added at a constant dosage of 0.5% by volume of concrete. A suitable amount of superplasticizer was used to obtain the required workability. For each mix proportion, six cube specimens were cast, demoulded after 24 hours, and cured in water until testing. The specimens were tested at curing ages of 7, 14, 28, and 56 days using a compression testing machine, and the compressive strength was calculated by dividing the maximum load at failure by the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

Fig.1 Compression Test

3.4.3 Split Tensile Strength Test:

The split tensile strength of concrete was determined using cylindrical specimens of size 150 mm diameter and 300 mm height. M40 grade concrete was prepared using Ordinary Portland Cement, fine aggregate, 20 mm nominal size coarse aggregate, with partial replacement of cement by Alccofine at 5%, 10%, and 15% and dolomite powder at 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%, while steel fibers were added at a constant dosage of 1% by volume of concrete. After casting, the specimens were demoulded after 24 hours and cured in water until the time of testing. For each mix proportion, the cylinders were tested at curing ages of 28, and 56 days using a compression testing machine by applying load diametrically. The split tensile strength was calculated based on the maximum load applied at failure.

Fig.2 Split Tensile Test

3.4.4 Flexural Strength Test:

The flexural strength of concrete was evaluated by testing beam specimens of size 100 mm × 100 mm × 500 mm. The concrete mix used was M40 grade, incorporating Alccofine and dolomite powder as partial replacements for cement and steel fibers as an additive at a constant percentage. Beam specimens

were demoulded after 24 hours and cured under water until testing. For each mix proportion, the beams were tested at curing ages of 28 and 56 days under two-point loading in a flexural testing machine. The load at failure was recorded, and the flexural strength of concrete was calculated using standard formulae.

Fig.3 Flexural Strength Test

3.4.5 Rebound Hammer Test

The rebound hammer test was conducted to assess the surface hardness and to obtain an indirect indication of the compressive strength of concrete. The test was carried out on cube specimens prepared for M40 grade concrete containing Alccofine and dolomite powder as partial replacements for cement, with steel fibers added as an additive. Before testing, the surface of each cube was cleaned and made smooth. The rebound hammer was held perpendicular to the concrete surface, and rebound readings were taken by pressing the plunger firmly against the specimen. For each cube, multiple readings were recorded at different locations and the average value was calculated. Six specimens were tested for each mix proportion at curing ages of 7, 28, and 56 days to study strength development and to compare the results with compressive strength obtained from destructive testing.

Fig.4 Rebound Hammer Test

3.4.6 Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV) Test

The ultrasonic pulse velocity test was performed to evaluate the internal quality, uniformity, and soundness of the concrete specimens. The test was carried out on M40 grade concrete cubes incorporating Alccofine and dolomite powder as cement replacements and steel fibers as an additive. The UPV equipment was used with transmitting and receiving transducers placed on opposite faces of the cube specimens. A suitable coupling medium was applied to ensure proper contact between the transducers and the concrete surface. The transit time of the ultrasonic pulse was recorded, and the pulse velocity was calculated for each specimen. For every mix proportion, six specimens were tested at curing ages of 7, 28, and 56 days. The obtained velocity values were used to assess concrete quality and to correlate the results with rebound hammer and compressive strength test outcomes.

Fig.5 Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test

4 TEST RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 GENERAL:

The experimental investigation included tests on both fresh and hardened concrete. The workability of freshly mixed concrete was evaluated using the slump test. Tests on hardened concrete included compressive strength and split tensile strength to assess the mechanical performance of the concrete mixes.

4.2 FRESH PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE

Workability of fresh concrete was evaluated using the slump cone test. A gradual reduction in workability was observed with the increase in the replacement levels of cement by Alccofine and dolomite powder, along with the addition of steel fibers. The slump values obtained for different mix proportions are presented in the graph below.

S. No	Mix id	Slump value (mm)
1	Nominal Mix	75
2	A5+D10+S0.5	72
3	A5+D20+S0.5	70
4	A5+D30+S0.5	68
5	A5+D40+S0.5	64
6	A10+D10+S0.5	78
7	A10+D20+S0.5	75
8	A10+D30+S0.5	71
9	A10+D40+S0.5	66
10	A15+D10+S0.5	80
11	A15+D20+S0.5	76
12	A15+D30+S0.5	72
13	A15+D40+S0.5	68

Table 1: Slump test results.

The slump test results indicate a gradual reduction in workability with increasing proportions of Alccofine and dolomite powder. This reduction is primarily due to the ultrafine nature of Alccofine and the filler effect of dolomite powder, which increase the surface area of cementitious materials and reduce the availability of free water in the mix. The addition of steel fibers further decreases slump because of increased internal friction and fiber–aggregate interaction, resulting in a stiffer mix. However, the use of an appropriate dosage of superplasticizer helped maintain medium workability suitable for mixing, placing,

and compaction. Overall, despite the reduction in slump at higher replacement levels, all mixes exhibited workability within acceptable limits for M40 grade concrete.

Fig.6 Slump Values

4.3 HARDENED PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE

Testing of hardened concrete is essential for evaluating the strength and overall quality of cement concrete. These tests help in confirming whether the concrete meets the required performance criteria. The testing methods adopted should be accurate, simple, and convenient to carry out in order to obtain reliable and consistent results.

4.4 COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST

Compressive strength is one of the most important properties of hardened concrete. The development of compressive strength in concrete primarily depends on the type, fineness, and proportion of the supplementary cementitious materials used, such as Alccofine and dolomite powder, along with the presence of steel fibers. Compressive strength tests were conducted using a compression testing machine, and the failure load and corresponding compressive strength of cube specimens were determined at curing ages of 7, 28, and 56 days.

Compression test			
Trial Mix	7 days	28 days	56 days
CTRL	31.67	48.17	50.22
T1	29.51	45.23	47.29
T2	29.28	44.8	46.83
T3	28.69	42.69	45.54
T4	27.43	40.21	41.37
T5	33.53	49.58	51.5
T6	31.28	47.86	49.8
T7	30.96	39.54	41.5
T8	29.77	36.51	38.5
T9	32.59	48	51
T10	30.54	45.74	48.5
T11	29.26	38.5	40.5
T12	28.21	36.43	38

Table 2: Compressive strength test results.

Below figure presents the variation in compressive strength of concrete containing different proportions of Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fibers at a constant fiber dosage of 0.5%. The results show a clear increase in compressive strength with increasing Alccofine and dolomite content up to an optimum level. The maximum compressive strength of 49.58 MPa at 28 days was achieved for mix T5, containing

10% Alccofine and 10% dolomite powder. This enhancement is attributed to the high reactivity of Alccofine and the filler effect of dolomite powder, which improve matrix densification. Beyond 10% replacement, a reduction in strength was observed due to excessive cement replacement and the inert nature of dolomite powder.

Fig.7 Compressive Strength Results

4.5 Split Tensile Strength Test

The split tensile strength of concrete was determined using cylindrical specimens in accordance with IS 5816:1999 at curing ages of 28, and 56 days. During testing, the specimens were placed horizontally between the compression platens and loaded diametrically until failure due to tensile splitting. The maximum load at failure was recorded, and the corresponding split tensile strength was calculated using standard equations. The average values for each mix were considered for analysis, and the results are presented graphically to illustrate the variation in tensile strength with curing age and mix composition.

Split Tensile Strength Test			
S. No	Mix ID	28 days	56 days
1	Nominal Mix	3.2	3.35
2	A5+D10+S0.5	3.05	3.2
3	A5+D20+S0.5	3	3.15
4	A5+D30+S0.5	2.8	2.93
5	A5+D40+S0.5	2.7	2.81
6	A10+D10+S0.5	3.5	3.65
7	A10+D20+S0.5	3.25	3.4
8	A10+D30+S0.5	2.85	3
9	A10+D40+S0.5	2.73	2.85
10	A15+D10+S0.5	3.45	3.6
11	A15+D20+S0.5	3.15	3.3
12	A15+D30+S0.5	2.75	2.9
13	A15+D40+S0.5	2.6	2.75

Table 3: Split Tensile Strength Test

Below figure presents the variation in Split tensile strength of concrete containing different proportions of Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fibers at a constant fiber dosage of 0.5%. The results show a clear increase in Split Tensile strength with increasing Alccofine and dolomite content up to an optimum level. The maximum Split Tensile strength of 3.5 MPa at 28 days was achieved for mix T5, containing 10% Alccofine and 10% dolomite powder. This enhancement is attributed to the high reactivity of Alccofine and

the filler effect of dolomite powder, which improve matrix densification. Beyond 10% replacement, a reduction in strength was observed due to excessive cement replacement and the inert nature of dolomite powder.

Figure 8: Split Tensile Strength Test Graph Values

4.6 Flexural Strength Test

The flexural strength of concrete was determined using prismatic beam specimens in accordance with IS 516 (Part 1): 1959 at curing ages of 28, and 56 days. The specimens were tested under two-point loading to ensure uniform bending, and the load was applied gradually until failure. The maximum load at failure was recorded, and the flexural strength was calculated using standard equations based on specimen dimensions and span length. Average flexural strength values were considered for each mix, and the results are presented graphically to show the influence of mix composition and curing age on flexural performance.

Flexural Strength Test			
S. No	Mix Proportion	28 days	56 days
1	Nominal Mix	4.2	4.4
2	A5+D10+S0.5	4	4.22
3	A5+D20+S0.5	3.9	4.1
4	A5+D30+S0.5	3.7	3.9
5	A5+D40+S0.5	3.6	3.72
6	A10+D10+S0.5	4.6	4.8
7	A10+D20+S0.5	4.25	4.45
8	A10+D30+S0.5	3.75	3.95
9	A10+D40+S0.5	3.65	3.85
10	A15+D10+S0.5	4.55	4.75
11	A15+D20+S0.5	4.1	4.3
12	A15+D30+S0.5	3.7	3.95
13	A15+D40+S0.5	3.6	3.8

Table 4: Flexural Strength Test

Below figure presents the variation in Flexural strength of concrete containing different proportions of Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fibers at a constant fiber dosage of 0.5%. The results show a clear increase in compressive strength with increasing Alccofine and dolomite content up to an optimum level. The maximum Flexural strength of 4.6 MPa at 28 days was achieved for mix T5, containing 10% Alccofine

and 10% dolomite powder. This enhancement is attributed to the high reactivity of Alccofine and the filler effect of dolomite powder, which improve matrix densification. Beyond 10% replacement, a reduction in strength was observed due to excessive cement replacement and the inert nature of dolomite powder.

Figure 9: Flexural Strength Test Graph Values

4.7 Rebound Hammer Test

The surface hardness of concrete was evaluated using the Rebound Hammer Test, which provides an indirect indication of compressive strength. The test was conducted on concrete specimens at 7, 28 and 56 days of curing in accordance with IS 13311 (Part 2): 1992. During testing, a Schmidt rebound hammer was applied perpendicular to the concrete surface, and rebound numbers were recorded at several locations on each specimen to minimize surface irregularities. The average rebound value obtained for each mix was considered to assess surface hardness and estimate the corresponding strength. The rebound numbers for different mix proportions are presented graphically in the following figures, showing the variation in rebound index values.

Rebound Hammer Test				
S. No	Mix Proportion	7 days	28 days	56 days
1	Nominal Mix	26.92	40.94	42.69
2	A5+D10+S0.5	25.08	38.45	40.2
3	A5+D20+S0.5	24.89	38.08	39.81
4	A5+D30+S0.5	24.39	36.29	38.71
5	A5+D40+S0.5	23.32	34.18	35.16
6	A10+D10+S0.5	28.5	42.14	43.78
7	A10+D20+S0.5	26.59	40.68	42.33
8	A10+D30+S0.5	26.32	33.61	35.28
9	A10+D40+S0.5	25.3	31.03	32.73
10	A15+D10+S0.5	27.7	40.8	43.35
11	A15+D20+S0.5	25.96	38.88	41.23
12	A15+D30+S0.5	24.87	32.73	34.43
13	A15+D40+S0.5	23.98	30.97	32.3

Table 5: Rebound Hammer Test

Figure 10: Flexural Strength Test Graph Values

4.8 Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV) Test

The quality and uniformity of concrete were evaluated using the Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test. The test was performed on $150 \times 150 \times 150$ mm cubes after 7, 28 and 56 days of self-curing, following the guidelines of **IS 13311 (Part 1): 1992**. In this method, an ultrasonic pulse was transmitted through the concrete specimen using a pair of transducers, and the time required for the pulse to travel across the specimen was recorded. Pulse velocity was then calculated and used to assess concrete quality, homogeneity, and presence of internal defects. The measured pulse velocity values for different mixes are plotted in the subsequent figures, showing the variation in ultrasonic pulse travel time and corresponding pulse velocities.

Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test				
S. No	Mix Proportion	7 days	28 days	56 days
1	Nominal Mix	4.6	4.74	4.89
2	A5+D10+S0.5	4.5	4.7	4.87
3	A5+D20+S0.5	4.43	4.62	4.98
4	A5+D30+S0.5	4.36	4.69	4.9
5	A5+D40+S0.5	4.49	4.75	5.06
6	A10+D10+S0.5	4.83	5.02	5.17
7	A10+D20+S0.5	4.57	4.87	4.83
8	A10+D30+S0.5	4.68	4.88	4.89
9	A10+D40+S0.5	4.8	4.8	4.99
10	A15+D10+S0.5	4.82	4.82	5.13
11	A15+D20+S0.5	4.66	4.97	4.96
12	A15+D30+S0.5	4.71	4.92	4.73
13	A15+D40+S0.5	4.97	4.91	4.96

Table 6: Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test

Figure 11: Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test Graph Values

CONCLUSION

This study examined the performance of M40 grade fiber-reinforced concrete incorporating Alccofine and dolomite powder as partial replacements for cement. Workability, mechanical properties, and non-destructive characteristics were evaluated at different curing ages. Based on the experimental results, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Workability decreased with increasing Alccofine, dolomite powder, and steel fiber content due to increased surface area and internal friction; however, all mixes maintained acceptable workability with the use of superplasticizer.
- The combined use of Alccofine and dolomite powder improved concrete microstructure through enhanced hydration and filler effects, leading to better matrix densification at lower replacement levels.
- The addition of steel fibers significantly enhanced split tensile and flexural strength by controlling crack propagation and improving post-cracking behavior.
- The optimum mix containing 10% Alccofine + 10% dolomite powder + 0.5% steel fibers (T5) achieved the maximum compressive strength of 49.58 MPa, split tensile strength of 3.50 MPa, and flexural strength of 4.6 MPa at 28 days.
- Non-destructive test results supported the mechanical test findings. The optimum mix recorded a rebound hammer value of 42.14 and a UPV value of approximately 5.02 km/s, classifying the concrete as excellent quality.
- Overall, the study confirms that the combined use of Alccofine and dolomite powder with steel fibers is an effective approach for producing sustainable, durable, and high-performance concrete with reduced cement content.

REFERENCES

- Akula, R., & Geetha, K.** (2020). Influence of Alccofine and steel fibers on mechanical properties of concrete. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*.
- Srinath, B. L. N., & Patnaikuni, C. K.** (2022). Review on performance of Alccofine as a supplementary cementitious material in concrete. *Materials Today: Proceedings*.
- Oviya, P., & Anusiya, K.** (2017). Mechanical properties of steel fiber reinforced concrete using hooked-end and crimped fibers. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*.
- Srinivasan, S.** (2020). Mechanical and durability performance of high-performance concrete using Alccofine-1203. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*.
- Gund, K. C., & Patwari, V. G.** (2020). Experimental study on partial replacement of cement with dolomite powder in concrete. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*.

6. **Kumar, R., & Dhaka, J.** (2016). Partial replacement of cement with Alccofine in concrete – A review. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*.
7. **Sawant, R. P., Kulkarni, A. B., & Patil, S. B.** (2019). Partial replacement of cement with Alccofine and marble dust in concrete. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*.
8. **Sumathi, A., Gowdham, K., & Mohan, K. S. R.** (2018). Strength and durability studies on Alccofine concrete with micro steel fibers. *Revista Romana de Materials*, 48(1), 58–63.
9. **Reddy, M. V., & Rao, K. B.** (2015). Effect of dolomite powder as partial cement replacement in concrete. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*.
10. **Barbhuiya, S. A.** (2011). Effects of dolomite powder on properties of self-compacting concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*.
11. **Banthia, N., & Trottier, J. F.** (1994). Concrete reinforced with deformed steel fibers: Bond and post-cracking behavior. *ACI Materials Journal*, 91(5), 435–446.
12. **Ghorpade, V. G.** (2013). Effect of steel fibers on strength and workability of concrete. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology*.
13. **Ramesh Babu, V.** (2014). Mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced concrete using mineral admixtures. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*.
14. **Naresh, C.** (2015). Workability characteristics of fiber-reinforced concrete with mineral fillers. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*.
15. **Ilango, V., & Mani, S.** (2008). Strength and durability of concrete using filler materials. *Indian Concrete Journal*.